

Studies in Quinones. Part II. Azonaphthols (Monophenylhydrazones of 1,4-Naphthaquinone)

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1,4-Naphthaquinone has been condensed with nine substituted phenylhydrazines. The products behave both as azonaphthols and monophenylhydrazones of the naphthaquinone.

In continuation of Part I¹ of this series the present work has been undertaken with a view to studying the compounds obtained from condensation of 1,4-naphthaquinone with 4-nitro-(I), 2-bromo-4-nitro-(II), 2-chloro-4-nitro-(III), 4-chloro-2-nitro-(IV), 2-chloro-4,6-dinitro-(V), 2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-(VI), 4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-(VII), 6-bromo-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-(VIII), and 6-chloro-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-(IX) phenylhydrazines.

The condensation products have been found to be identical with those formed by coupling the diazonium salts of the corresponding anilines with α -naphthol.

The products, though predominantly azophenolic, are found to be tautomeric in character as these not only form salts with aqueous sodium hydroxide and acetyl derivatives with acetic anhydride (like phenolic compounds) but also give dihydrazones with phenylhydrazine (like ketonic or quinonoid compound). Absorption spectra studies (which will be communicated later) reveal that these have predominantly quinonoid structure in nitrobenzene, acetic acid and phenolic in pyridine and dimethylformamide.

The azonaphthols are coloured compounds varying from deep red to dark chocolate in shade. These are slightly soluble in ethanol and more readily in acetic acid from which these can be crystallised.

EXPERIMENTAL

Azonaphthols.—Following the procedures described in the previous communication¹, these have been obtained by condensing nitrophenylhydrazines with 1,4-naphthaquinone and also by coupling nitrobenzenediazonium halides with α -naphthol. A mixture of the azo compounds from the two methods showed no depression in m.p.

The acetyl and phenylhydrazine derivatives of these azonaphthols have been prepared by following the procedure described earlier¹.

Analytical data and characteristics of azonaphthols obtained from different phenylhydrazines and 1,4-naphthaquinone together with those of their acetyl and phenylhydrazine derivatives are recorded in Tables II and I respectively.

1. Joshi, Deorha, and Joshi, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 395.

TABLE I
 Acetyl derivatives. Phenylhydrazones.

*S.No.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	M. P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	160°	Red	$C_{18}H_{13}O_4N_3$	N : 12.32%	12.54%	300°(d)	Brick-red	$C_{21}H_{17}O_4N_3$	N : 18.12%	18.27%
2.	158°	Reddish brown	$C_{18}H_{12}O_4N_3Br$	Br : 19.11	10.32	300°(d)	Dull-red	$C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_3Br$	Br : 17.08	17.31
3.	163°	Brown	$C_{18}H_{12}O_4N_3Cl$	Cl : 9.78	9.61	285°(d)	"	$C_{21}H_{16}O_4N_3Cl$	Cl : 8.31	8.50
4.	148°	Reddish brown	$C_{18}H_{11}O_4N_3Cl$	Cl : 9.43	9.61	270°	Brown-red	$C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_3Cl$	Cl : 8.29	8.50
5.	178°	Brownish yellow	$C_{18}H_{11}O_6N_4Cl$	Cl : 8.69	8.56	262°	Deep orange	$C_{22}H_{15}O_4N_6Cl$	Cl : 7.48	7.67
6.	175°	Reddish brown	$C_{18}H_{11}O_6N_4Br$	Br : 17.27	17.43	258°	Orange-red	$C_{22}H_{15}O_4N_6Br$	Br : 15.63	15.78
7.	210°	Do	$C_{18}H_{14}O_6N_4$	N : 14.04	14.21	260°	Red	$C_{23}H_{18}O_4N_6$	N : 19.23	19.00
8.	180°	Brown-red	$C_{19}H_{13}O_6N_4Br$	Br : 17.11	10.01	263°	Dull red	$C_{23}H_{17}O_4N_6Br$	Br : 15.47	15.35
9.	186°	Do	$C_{18}H_{13}O_6N_4Cl$	Cl : 0.04	8.28	265°	Deep red	$C_{23}H_{17}O_4N_6Cl$	Cl : 7.03	7.45

*The number of azophenols corresponds to those listed in Table II.
 (d) denotes decomposition.

TABLE II

Azophenols from 1,4-naphthaquinone and substituted phenylhydrazines.

S.No.	Phenyl hydrazine	Azonaphthol (1'-azo-4'-ol).	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	I	4-Nitro-	286°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃	N : 14.47%	14.33%
2.	II	2-Bromo-4-nitro-	257°	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Br	Br : 21.18	21.50
3.	III	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	250°	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 11.21	10.84
4.	IV	4-Chloro-2-nitro-	244°	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 10.49.	10.84
5.	V	2-chloro-4,6-dinitro-	218°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.78	9.53
6.	VI	2-Bromo-4,6-dinitro-	210°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₅ N ₄ Br	Br : 19.32	19.18
7.	VII	4,6-Dinitro-3-methyl-	232°	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₅ N ₄	N : 16.32	15.91
8.	VIII	6-Bromo-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-	230°	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₄ Br	Br : 18.24	18.56
9.	IX	6-Chloro-2, 4-dinitro-3-methyl-	218°	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.41	9.18

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